

On the Reliability of Artificial Intelligence Systems

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Abstract—This article proposes a set of concrete technical requirements for trustworthy artificial intelligence methods. Although these requirements do not cover the social, ethical, or regulatory dimensions, they do cover the technical aspects of the complete life-cycle of an AI system, from its design and operational monitoring and control to its behaviour when it fails. The article concludes with an outline for an ambitious but realistic research plan that can advance the state of the art in the direction of reliable AI systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

As *artificial intelligence (AI)* technologies, and most prominently among them *machine learning (ML)*, are reaching the maturity needed for widespread application, the discussion on the safeguards and policies that need to be in place is picking up pace and volume. This discussion usually conflates multiple dimensions under the term of *trustworthy AI*: The technical evaluation of AI technologies with respect to their being fit for purpose; The policies that the human operators are asked to implement and the accountability of these operators with respect to how faithfully and aptly they implement them; And the access points offered by the system to its human operators to effectively monitor and control a deployed system.

In this article we will discuss the concept of *reliability*. Although reliability alone does not completely cover what is usually understood as AI trustworthiness, it does cut across all its dimensions:

- *Reliability* is not completely covered by measuring accuracy and relevant performance metrics. To be reliable a system should cover non-functional requirements such as graceful degradation (rather than collapse) in adverse deployment conditions, maintainability, and robustness in time.
- *Design for testability (DFT)*, primarily in microelectronics, is the addition of features already at design time that do not satisfy functional requirements but make it easier to test the system and to diagnose failures.
- *Empowering human operators* to monitor and control through means offered to them by the system to diagnose failures and to react to these failures.

The aim of this position paper is to interpret these general objectives as concrete technical requirements and to argue that the proposed requirements are ambitious but realistic based on the current state of the art.

II. MONITORING AND CONTROL

Although the term artificial intelligence subsumes a wide variety of algorithms, what is usually of concern in the context

of trustworthiness are connectionist, or neuro-inspired, *artificial neural networks (ANN)*. These systems encode knowledge in the form of a complex network of simple processing nodes, so that the decisions made by the system depend on how the nodes interact rather than on the processing that takes place on any one node.

At the current state of the art ANNs with millions of nodes can be built with commodity computer hardware, while major ANN instances exceed 100 billion nodes. As the logic behind each decision is distributed throughout the network, at these scales it is out of the question that ANNs can be monitored or controlled applying conventional software engineering. That is, it is completely impossible for an engineer to follow the processing steps from inputs to outputs and, even more so, to control the outputs by directly editing the ‘program’, the parameters (weights) of the connections.

As a result, monitoring is restricted to measuring errors in its outputs. Control is also limited to deciding on the network architecture, setting the learning rate and other hyper-parameters, and augmenting or improving the training dataset. These are important decisions that can dramatically affect performance, and we will revisit them below in the context of the degrees of freedom offered to system developers. But in the current context of operating a deployment, it cannot be realistically expected that the system can be re-designed and re-trained to address minor failures. The only action that the field operator can perform is to ignore or shut down the system and send it back for re-design and re-training, possibly attaching the datapoints that demonstrate the failure.

From a reliability point of view, this creates two problems: it causes system non-availability even in minor failures that in other technical systems would normally be addressed on the spot; and it enervates the feedback channel of work-arounds and improvisations that is invaluable for iterative improvement.

To give an example of an interpretable and editable machine learning system, consider GAM Changer (Wang et al., 2022). GAM Changer applies *Generalized Additive Models (GAM)* to the medical domain and allows physicians to analyse, validate, and intuitively edit models so that model behaviours align with their knowledge and values. Naturally, this is mostly facilitated by the fact that GAMs are the linear combination of the input values, a straight-forward and intuitive model. Manually ‘patching’ ANN deployments would be a lot less straightforward, but no less desirable.

REQUIREMENT: In order to take full advantage of the *virtuous circle* of iteratively improving through

usage, active deployments should be able to contribute not only training data but also locally developed improvisations and work-arounds, which are then generalized by the vendor into improvements for all deployments.

III. PERFORMANCE IN THE LAB IS NOT RELIABILITY

Classical ANNs have three fully-connected layers of nodes, but the recent *deep learning* revolution spreads nodes along a deeper architecture with more than the three theoretically required layers. Different deep learning architectures have been found to have their respective benefits and drawbacks for different applications, but in all cases a deep ANN will have a dramatically smaller number of possible connection configurations than a fully connected ANN and thus much larger networks can be realistically trained. This is a very promising development, not only because it has allowed deep networks to scale but also because layers are, effectively, levels of increasingly abstract representations of the input data (Bengio and LeCun, 2007; Bengio and Delalleau, 2011). This already makes ANNs less opaque and affords opportunities for human inspection and manipulation.

Recent developments in computer vision serve as a prime example of how the architecture can have profound effects on the behaviour of the system. In machine vision, the straightforward, linear *Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)* architecture originally dominated the state of the art (Krizhevsky et al., 2012; Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014), but was superseded by more complex *Residual Neural Network (ResNet)* architectures that include connections that implement recurrent layers and layer skipping (He et al., 2016; Szegedy et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2018). In a parallel development, the YOLO architecture re-frames the idea of convolution in order to overcome the inability of the original CNNs to properly take into account context (Redmon et al., 2016), with its latest editions also achieving state-of-the-art results.

What is important to note in the above timeline is that although networks do get larger over time, it was not larger networks alone that achieved major strides in performance but also an ever-improving understanding of how different architectures behave and the accumulation of expertise on how to best engineer architectures that emphasise benefits relevant to the application at hand. This corroborates to the importance of the first requirement above, although in this context the improvements were the result of the experience gained through lab experimentation rather than deployments. But the argument is again that improvement came not through exposing a black-box learner to increasingly complex and voluminous data but through directly engineering the structure of the learner.

Notwithstanding these advances, ANNs remain relatively flimsy, which is manifested both by the ObjectNet dataset and adversarial attacks. *ObjectNet* is a collection of images of common household objects photographed from strange angles or positioned in strange ways, such as upside down. Testing the state of the art on ObjectNet has given accuracies that are half of what is reported on the usual datasets (Barbu et al., 2019), demonstrating how all machine vision systems fail to

capture the essential properties of these objects and rely on superficial visual clues.

Subsequent developments such as *Visual Transformers (ViT)* have greatly increased their robustness on ObjectNet (Dosovitskiy et al., 2021), but the statement above about their lack of robustness stands as demonstrated by *adversarial attacks* developed subsequently to their introduction (Wei et al., 2022). Adversarial attacks also exploit the fact that ANNs do not analyse or sanity-check their decisions. Each layer is a mathematical function that maps arrays of values to other values, and the complete network maps an array of RGB values to a decision value without connecting these outputs to any wider system of knowledge about the world and the objects in it. Adversarial attacks perturb images by slightly pushing the RGB values in the image towards values that yield features (intermediate layer outputs) that push the decision to a different object. Where a human would immediately recognize the correct object maybe with the colours looking a bit strange, the ANN will *confidently* make absurd decisions. Adversarial attacks have been shown to cut the accuracy of state-of-the-art networks (both CNN-based and ResNet-based) in *half or even less* and fully understanding and mitigating the phenomenon is an open research question (Arnab et al., 2018). Finally, adversarial attacks are not restricted to machine vision but are ubiquitous across the spectrum of deep learning applications (Jia et al., 2022; Ghaffari Laleh et al., 2022; Brophy et al., 2023; He et al., 2023).

The expectation is that deep learning engineers will eventually devise a way to counter adversarial attacks, just as they have eventually devised an architecture that is robust to ObjectNet angles and positions. But the underlying lack of reliability is still there waiting for more weakness to be discovered: When ANNs fail, they fail with confidence rather than recognizing an input as being an anomaly.

REQUIREMENT: In order to be reliable, artificial intelligence tools should either succeed or recognize that they have failed, by internalizing the understanding that the form (visual or other) presented by the input data is a superficial representation of underlying processes and mechanisms. A reliable artificial intelligence must not just map inputs to outputs, but it must use inputs to hypothesise about the processes and mechanisms that generated these inputs, so that it can reliably either correctly analyse what is being observed or raise an exception upon detecting incongruence and anomaly.

IV. DESIGN FOR TESTABILITY AND EDITABILITY

For pragmatic (Pearl, 2019) as well as regulatory (Pekka Ala-Pietilä et al., 2019) reasons, the deployment of opaque AI tools is meeting resistance especially in applications where the stakes are high. This has directed the interest of the research community to *explainable AI (xAI)*. To summarize recent surveys (Minh et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2022; Holzinger et al., 2022), xAI is clustered in two main approaches:

- Local explanations show the part or parts of the input and their attributes that mostly contributed to make a

specific decision. Techniques such as masking allow local explanations to be applied to black-box models.

- Global explanations are typically generated from *surrogate models*. These are models in a human-interpretable and intuitive formalism that are trained using the outputs of the full model.

Local explanations can greatly help with error analysis, but fall short of being able to provide both the control and the insights about how the model perceives the world put forward as requirements above. As for surrogate models, as Rudin (2019) convincingly argues, they are often misleading. To what one can add that there is also no way to port patches from the surrogate back to original model.

There are, however, several methods in the recent literature that move in the direction of explaining the original model. ANNs construct a *latent space* wherein they manipulate value vectors. Typically, learning algorithms apply bias towards dimensions that are as uncorrelated as possible so that all value vectors are possible and no parts of the space are left unused. This data-driven bias gives efficiency, but creates a space where the dimensions have no meaning that could be communicated or explained. *Concept whitening* (Chen et al., 2020) is a different learning bias that forces the dimensions of the latent space to align with pre-configured concepts of interest. An alternative approach exploits top-down feedback to take into account an explicit context. Where ResNet and similar *recurrent* ANNs would feed intermediate layers' outputs backwards in order to provide context, *mid-vision feedback* (Maynord et al., 2023) allows pushing back feedback that is not by necessity from the same network. Although this possibility is not yet fully explored, this does in principle allow pushing back a context constructed from categorical, symbolic knowledge.

These are new approaches to an old problem in AI, that of interfacing the data-driven conceptualizations (ways to organize objects) that emerge from machine learning with human-understandable and human-curated symbolic knowledge representations. Having a shared, or at least compatible, conceptual foundation is a promising path for explaining how AI slices and dices the world as it processes inputs to make a decision, so the recent drive for xAI has made *neuro-symbolic* approaches a prominent future work item in the field (Kautz, 2022).

Although neuro-symbolic AI can give us the transparency and editability we require, it is worth noting that many approaches impose upon the AI our *prior* conceptualization, rather than having the AI and the engineer establish a *new* and *shared* conceptualization. This violates the DFT objective we stated in the Introduction: forcing a prior conceptualization reshapes and constrains functional features in order to facilitate testability, instead of adding non-functional features. This can lead to missing an opportunity to discover in the data new, previously unnoticed, attributes and patterns.

REQUIREMENT: The reliability requirements stated above should be satisfied by improving AI methods and by adding non-functional features that facilitate monitor and control.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed requirements might be ambitious, but the arguments presented to support them indicate that they are both needed and attainable. Needed because, although reliability is not the only aspect of trust that AI systems need to gain, it is the hardest to attain within the technical domain. It is also one, especially through monitor and control, that enables non-technical discussions on policy and accountability to be grounded on technical feasibility.

Regarding the extent to which they are realistic, the recent state of the art presented here is promising. To start with, explainability is mentioned by Maynord et al. (2023) as a potential positive side-effect of mid-vision feedback, although without providing technical details on what is envisaged. But one can see that mid-vision feedback can be integrated with concepts from concept whitening in order to have a way to inspect what is represented in the intermediate layers of the network, at least at the level of characteristic examples. What mid-vision feedback provides to concept whitening is a way to operate without the need to supervise the system with characteristic samples of each concept. Concept whitening as originally formulated by Chen et al. (2020) requires detailed supervision that does not scale well and (most importantly) restricts the degrees of freedom of the network. In mid-vision feedback, on the other hand, the network is free to look for novel ways to slice and dice the world as such ways emerge from the data, but the network does not have a way to communicate these new concepts and build a shared conceptualization between the human operator and itself. A promising path might be to have the network organize the world, present this organization by selecting or synthesising samples of each concept, and provide the operator with a way to disallow concepts. The operator has in mind a task that the system is trying to achieve and flags concepts that should be used as features for subsequent layers because they are biased, coincidental, or otherwise not warranted. Formally defining and actually implementing what it means to disallow a concept might be difficult in a way that generalizes across network architectures, but future research can implement this in individual architectures and subsequently look for commonalities that can be factored out.

This line of thought naturally brings into the discussion the concept of *modularization*. Since the only explicit boundaries between network nodes are the layers, any conceptualization like the one described above will have to be based on clusters of the feature vectors propagated between layers. In the research plan described above we made no reference to *how* intermediate concepts are used by subsequent layers, and the operator had to exclude concepts on the basis of their being *potentially* used in a way that is counter to their intuition about the task.

It would be an obvious advantage to be able to communicate how concepts are actually used. Note, however, that in non-trivial applications we expect large numbers of concepts that all contribute to the next layer without necessarily having some weights stand out as particularly prominent. To be able to meaningfully communicate how concepts from different

layer interact, we need to modularize the trained network into human-biteable chunks so that the operator can inspect them one by one without having to retain in working memory the complete set dependencies from one layer to the next. Naturally, as argued above, this modularization would ideally be posterior to training rather than an imposed prior.

Notwithstanding an imminent breakthrough in clustering methods, this will not be possible in the general case. A reasonable compromise can be imposing a *defeasible* prior modularization. To make this more concrete, suppose a prior conceptualization, broken down into layers (of abstraction and of the network) and imposing mutual exclusiveness or other axioms between the concepts in each layer. The network would have to either refine the concept definitions or decide that a re-organization of the concepts of a layers would improve the overall result in a way analogous to how mid-vision feedback simultaneously uses and shapes the context represented in intermediate layers. *Neurosymbolic AI* (Saker et al., 2022) and *automatic differentiation* (Baydin et al., 2018) can make it possible to define and train more complex and more dynamic architectures, where well-defined modules interact in ways that are predefined but can change in the face of empirical evidence. These approaches assume a logical (in Neurosymbolic AI) or programmatic (in automatic differentiation) representation as the structural backbone of the network; both approaches propose methods for back-propagating loss through the complete network, exploiting the usual end-to-end supervision and avoiding detailed supervision.

As the structure of the network can be inspected and edited, the operator can, for example, remove the dependency between two concepts from different layers instead of completely banning the concept in the earlier layer. To give a concrete example, consider the infamous example of classifying dogs vs. wolves based on the green or snowy background rather than on the actual animal (Ribeiro et al., 2016). Banning all concepts characterizing backgrounds does not require an understand of how concepts interact, but would render the network task-specific and not amenable to refinement to other tasks. Banning connections from background concepts to animal concepts would be a better way to communicate with a network, as it endows it with a more accurate and more generally useful piece of world knowledge.

We propose the dog vs wolf scenario, and many similar famous misclassifications from the deep vision literature and lore, as a good test case for research in neurosymbolic AI. Specifically, we propose that the test case is that a human operator is able to fix a misclassification by editing the logical part of the network and that an expert operator will be able to see what to edit without unforeseeable and catastrophic side-effects, just like an expert programmer can debug and correct a program with minimal suffering from long-distance side-effects.

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